

THE USING OF THE MODERN METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract. *The process of globalization requires people to learn several foreign languages in addition to their mother tongue. Current research shows that starting this process at an early age is more effective. In our country, strict attention is paid to this issue, programs are being developed based on a new approach to teaching foreign languages, especially English, in cooperation with the world's leading organizations and universities. In the last 3 years, this process is developing especially in preschool education. Large-scale projects on teaching English are being implemented in state-owned and private pre-school educational organizations. This article highlights the importance of using educational games in teaching Shet languages, especially English, in early childhood, and the easy acquisition of language skills through various games.*

Keywords: *foreign language, early age language learning, educational game, activity, fine motor skills, hand-eye coordination, active learning types, block play in English, role-playing games, hand-made.*

Introduction: Today, every compatriot notices and observes unprecedented changes in the field of preschool education. It is no exaggeration to say that the preschool education system, which is considered the foundation of education, has not received such systematic and complementary attention and practical support from the state. The issue of solving the accumulated problems in the field and ensuring the full education of children aged 3 to 7 years was put forward by the head of our country as an urgent task. The reason is that kindergartens, instead of performing the function of an educational institution, have become institutions where parents look after children while they are at work, low coverage, buildings in disrepair, used for other purposes, methodologically incomplete, pedagogues solving complex problems such as social protection and low wages was an issue that could not be delayed. Over the next 20 years, the number of state-owned preschool educational institutions decreased by 45%, and only 818,000 of 2.45 million children were enrolled in preschool educational institutions. Inadequate state of infrastructure and material and technical base of pre-school education organizations did not allow to ensure full coverage of children with pre-school education. The meeting held on August 16, 2017 was a meeting that will remain in the history of the preschool education system. On this day, the President of our country spoke about the strengthening of the state's national genetic fund and defined many directions for the development of the first stage of education. In particular, important tasks have been assigned to structurally reform the pre-school education system, to fully cover children in these educational organizations.

"When we talking about the education system, which is of decisive importance in our lives, we have to repeat the wise words of our grandfather Abdulla Avloni: education is a matter of life and death for us," said the President. - No matter what field we choose; we

cannot achieve any changes or a prosperous life without educating modern mature personnel. Preparation of such personnel, a healthy gene pool of the nation, begins first of all with the preschool education system.

Up to now, these indicators are giving their effective results, teaching a second language is also considered as the main issue in preschool education organizations.

Pupils of pre-school education organizations in rural areas usually grow up in conditions far away from the English language environment, and children's thinking remains abstract, the process of acquiring new knowledge is always based on emotions. Therefore, teachers of English language to children of kindergarten age make full use of objects, flashcards and other teaching aids around the children through easy methods. When teaching words like "banana" and "apple", children can simultaneously learn new words for color by showing them fruits like banana and apple. Teachers teach them how to use them in a foreign language through the things in the training room to organize training sessions. Of course, the teacher's methodology plays a big role in the use of materials during teaching. For example, when teaching related words, you first show the child the object and encourage him to say it, the children pronounce the words, and the new word is repeated again using the pictures on the cards to reinforce the word they said. . In teaching words, teachers can determine the content of the text, and in order to attract the children's attention, the teacher can draw their picture on the board by pronouncing the words together with them. Therefore, currently in China, a teacher is required to have drawing skills. This not only reduces the difficulty of teaching, but also helps children gradually consolidate the knowledge they have learned. In order for children to feel their progress in the process of learning English, it is necessary to have a perfect approach to each educational activity. That is the only way children are motivated to learn. Nowadays, Chinese kindergarten-age children are more receptive to new knowledge, so the teaching programs in kindergartens have been intensified accordingly.

Using songs and total physical responsible games to improve the classroom environment.

Creating a flexible training room atmosphere is sometimes more important than any training method. In the room at the beginning of the lesson with a nice English song, all children led by the teacher sang together and danced a little to its tune. This in itself will help them exercise their bodies, become more energetic and memorize the lyrics of the song faster. The English environment, importantly, allows for a natural entry into a good learning atmosphere. Children's ability to self-control is weak, and it is difficult for them to concentrate and hold their attention during the whole lesson. Therefore, the teacher should provide songs that children like to listen to, poems or quick sayings to practice the language, or if not, an animated cartoon that children like.

Cartoons. While learning a foreign language, children do not understand the words in the cartoon, but they try to understand the words they use through the actions of the characters in the cartoon. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn the language.

The role of gestures and facial expressions in raising the level of education.

Through gestures and facial expressions: When the teacher speaks something to the children or gives an order, for example, when using gestures, the child will understand these words.

Gesture is the most important teaching method of English language. Almost every educator knows that animal gestures are the easiest way in the preparation process (monkey) shows his appearance in a slightly bent position. For children with an imitative nature, this will be very interesting and immediately make them say the name of the animal represented. this will encourage

you to remember the newly learned words. Taking into account that the majority of young families now have one child, the children of such families have a very masculine character. At this point, we should mention that it will not be easy for a teacher to find a way to the hearts of children with such a character. A teacher should have a kind eye and a gentle smile, this will awaken the love for a special teacher in children. The gesture method helps children to act independently and learn a foreign language in an interesting way. Through this, we create an interesting atmosphere for learning a foreign language.

Using puzzle games to strengthen acquired skills.

It is necessary to increase the child's interest in the English language from a young age, it is necessary to force him to speak even if there is a mistake, only then the child being educated will be able to overcome the obstacles in front of him and speak without fear. If we make a foreign language lesson not a lesson, but a game, it will increase the interest of young children even more. At the same time, their level of activity also increases. There are many types of games, for example, a teacher can play the game "what's in the bag" with children. Put the small objects in the room in a bag and let the children take them one by one and the children say the names of these objects in English. "Is it a banana (an apple, an orange)?" the teacher begins the assessment and awards the group with the most points. With this, children's interest in foreign languages will grow.

Competitions among children are very important, because it is necessary to form a sense of competition in children from a young age. That's the only reason every child is motivated and interested in language.

Use of multimedia to increase the effectiveness of teaching.

Teaching through multimedia gives the teacher great opportunities. In this way, it is possible to increase the interest of children to a high level and to attract their attention for a long time. Through this, we can see that children's language skills have increased. If our topic is "Animals", we first use their sounds to teach the names of different animals. Childhood can be considered the best time to develop a person's thinking ability. Therefore, teachers of preschool educational organizations should apply science based on the needs (interests) of children. It is necessary to train thinking exercises and mental development with the help of new multimedia technologies, to form the ability to hear, recognize colors, and choose shapes. It is very important to increase children's ability to receive external information and to help them develop multifaceted thinking. We can often find lameness in the ability to hear in a foreign language in children of preschool age, which means that children do not take enough listening lessons. In real life, we can see children quietly watching an animated cartoon under the TV. Today, the time has come to provide preschool education organizations with high technologies. It is necessary to listen to cartoon lessons in foreign languages constantly, developing the child's foreign language skills from kindergarten will help him to easily accept all knowledge at the next stage. At the stage of kindergarten age, the development of language skills is mainly formed through constant imitation, and many roles often appear in cartoons through imitation. Therefore, when watching a cartoon, we can see the changes in children's actions. Therefore, we can use the cartoon as an effective educational tool, which helps to improve the educational efficiency of children. Nowadays, some parents are very concerned about children's interest in cartoons, but in fact, in the development of young children, their fantasy is the main factor in the formation of their worldview. Therefore, in teaching, we can use the remote control method of the United States of America, that is, cartoons as a way to influence children's language development. We all know that at this stage, young

children learn their thinking skills and language skills from real-life experiences, especially for young children at this stage, communication with cartoons can expand their remote sensory aspect and help to improve children's language skills. does.

In fact, it is better to start learning a foreign language from a very young age. Since the brain activity of young children continues to develop without stopping, they have the ability to receive new information much faster than adults whose brain activity is fully formed. It is appropriate to plan a lesson taking into account these features. For example, the use of games, pictures, songs and poems, and cartoons is an effective way to teach foreign language to children of preschool age.

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